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Research Article

Development and Validation of UV-Visible Spectrophotometric and RP-HPLC Methods for Quantification of Mangiferin in Bulk Drug According to ICH Q2(R1) Guidelines

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ABSTRACT

Mangiferin is a bioactive xanthone C-glycoside found highly in *Mangifera indica* and several medicinal plants. It exhibits promising antioxidant, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective activities. There are only few studies reported the method development of simple, low-cost UV-visible spectrophotometric and RP-HPLC methods with validation parameters suitable for routine quality control of mangiferin in bulk and herbal formulations, revealing a critical research gap in accessible analytical methodologies even though it has reputed pharmaceutical importance. The present study aims to develop and validate rapid, economical and reliable UV-visible spectrophotometric and RP-HPLC methods for the accurate quantification of mangiferin in accordance with ICH Q2(R1) guidelines. In this current research, UV-visible spectrophotometry was performed using methanol and water. RP-HPLC was performed using Shimadzu C8 column (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) which was maintained at 25 °C with isocratic elution using 10 mM ammonium acetate buffer (pH 3): acetonitrile (80:20 v/v) as a mobile phase with flow rate of 1 ml/min and detection was performed at 257 nm. Both methods show excellent linearity from 1 to 5 μg/ml with correlation coefficients of 0.999 for UV and 0.9989 for RP-HPLC. The retention time for mangiferin in RP-HPLC method was obtained at 2.9 min. Limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) were found to be 5.21 μg/ml and 15.81 μg/ml for UV, and 5.22 μg/ml and 15.81 μg/ml for RP-HPLC, respectively. Precision parameters show %RSD less than 2% for repeatability, intra-day, and inter-day measurements confirming its high reproducibility. All other validation parameters such as ruggedness, robustness, and specificity complied with ICH requirements. As there is an increasing demand for standardized herbal products, these simple, cost-effective and fully validated UV and

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RP-HPLC methods provide practical approaches for routine quality assurance, batch to batch consistency and regulatory compliance.

INTRODUCTION

Mangiferin is a bioactive xanthone C-glycoside with the IUPAC name 1,3,6,7-tetrahydroxy-2-[(2S,3R,4R,5S,6R)-3,4,5-trihydroxy-6-(hydroxymethyl)oxan-2-yl]xanthen-9-one [1,2]. It was first isolated from *Mangifera indica* L. (Anacardiaceae) [2,3,7].

It is found in at least 16 plant families, such as Anacardiaceae, Iridaceae, and Gentianaceae [2,3,4,6]. It is especially common in mango extracts [1-4,6]. Mangiferin functions as a strong plant metabolite with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, and neuroprotective effects [1,2,4,5]. It works by scavenging free radicals, reducing oxidative stress, inhibiting inflammatory substances, and influencing cellular pathways linked to apoptosis and immune responses [1,2,4,5,8].

There are only few studies reported in UV-visible spectrophotometric and RP-HPLC methods with existing challenges include time consuming optimization, limited specificity in UV-Vis and high equipment dependency in HPLC. UV-Vis studies provide rapid, non-destructive absorbance based analysis but lacks separation for impurities, whereas RP-HPLC provides high resolution for polar compounds but often used C18 columns and acidic mobile phases with complex mobile phases [9-11].

This study aims to develop and validate UV-Vis and RP-HPLC methods for mangiferin estimation which include method optimization, validation per ICH guidelines (linearity, precision, accuracy, LOD/LOQ, robustness) with enhanced sensitivity, linearity, reduced run times (~10 min), low %RSD (<2%) for precision and eco-friendly solvent

utilization, addressing demerits like high LOD in UV methods and reproducibility/ruggedness by integrating with hybrid UV-HPLC for cost-efficiency.

Chemical structure:

Figure 1: Chemical Structure of Mangiferin

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals:

Mangiferin was purchased from BLD Pharmatech (India) Pvt. Ltd, Hyderabad. Methanol AR grade was procured from Sigma Aldrich Chemicals Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai. Acetonitrile HPLC grade was purchased from Sigma Aldrich Chemicals Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai. Ammonium acetate was bought from Titan Biotech Ltd., New Delhi. Acetic acid was obtained from Amichem Research Lab LLP, Dehradun, Uttarakhand.

Apparatus and conditions

Spectroscopic conditions

Shimadzu UV-1650PC UV spectrophotometer, which has a silicon photodiode detector and UV probe software was used for this study.

1. Selection of solvent

Methanol was used to prepare the initial stock solution of Mangiferin and distilled water was used for subsequent serial dilutions.

2. Selection of wavelength

Based on absorbance shown in UV scanning for Mangiferin from 200 to 400 nm, 257 nm is found to be the appropriate wavelength for detection and that λ_{max} is used for the study.

Chromatographic conditions

The Shimadzu (CBM-20A) HPLC device which was equipped with Shimadzu-SPD-M20A diode array detector and LC lab solution software was used. The Shim pack solar C8 column with dimensions 250 mm x 4 mm x 5 μ m was used.

1. Selection of wavelength

The UV spectra were used to determine the wavelength and 257 nm was chosen because of its good absorbance. Therefore, based on the spectrum it was determined that the detection wavelength under study is 257 nm.

2. Fixed chromatographic conditions

Method development was carried out with mobile phase 10mM ammonium acetate pH 3: acetonitrile (80:20). At a detection wavelength of 257 nm, the flow rate, column temperature, and sample volume were adjusted to 1 ml/min, 25°C, and 20 μ l, respectively.

Preparation of stock solutions:

UV-visible Spectroscopy

Stock 1

10 mg of Mangiferin was weighed and transferred into 10ml volumetric flasks and the volume was made up to 10 ml using a 1:1 ratio of methanol to water. The mixture was then sonicated for 15 minutes until thoroughly dissolved. The final concentration of Mangiferin was 1000 μ g/ml.

Stock 2

A 1 ml aliquot of Mangiferin from stock solution 1 was transferred to 10 ml volumetric flasks and the volume was made up to 10 ml with water. The solution was sonicated for 15 minutes, and the final concentration of Mangiferin was found to be 100 μ g/ml.

Construction of Calibration curve:

To achieve a final concentration range of 1-5 μ g/ml, aliquots of 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, and 0.5 ml of Mangiferin solutions from stock 2 were transferred into 10 ml volumetric flasks and filled with water up to the mark. The standard solutions of Mangiferin were scanned at 257 nm and calibration curve was created by plotting concentration on the x-axis and absorbance on the y-axis.

RP-HPLC

Preparation of 10mM ammonium acetate buffer (pH 3)

770 mg of ammonium acetate was weighed and dissolved with about 800ml water (HPLC grade) in a beaker. pH was adjusted to the target value by using dilute acetic acid solution. The solution was filtered through a membrane of 0.45 μ m into a measuring flask and sufficient water was added to produce 1000 ml.

Preparation of mobile phase

A mixture of 10mM ammonium acetate buffer (pH 3) and acetonitrile in an 80:20 ratio was prepared and degassed in an ultra sonicator for 15 minutes.

Preparation of standard stock solution

10 mg of Mangiferin standard was taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up to 10 ml with mobile phase (10mM ammonium acetate buffer of pH 3 and acetonitrile in 80:20

ratio). Then the mixture was sonicated for 15 min to dissolve it completely. From the stock solution, working standard solutions were prepared by appropriate dilutions with mobile phase. Calibration curve was plotted from the concentration range of 1-5 µg/ml for Mangiferin.

RESULTS

Method development and optimization of Spectroscopic conditions

To determine concentration of an analyte, with a cuvette containing a sample solution, a UV-Visible spectrophotometer detects the light intensity and compares it to the light intensity prior to the sample passage through the cuvette. A light source, a sample holder, a dispersive element to separate the various wavelengths and an appropriate detector are the essential parts of a UV-Visible spectrophotometer [12]. The analytical technique measures the absorption of monochromatic light by colourless substances in the 200–400 nm near ultraviolet region of the spectrum [13]. The UV scanning at 200-400nm for Mangiferin showed that 257 nm is the suitable wavelength for detection as per maximum absorbance. The spectrum is shown in Figure 2.

Method development and optimization of chromatographic conditions

To achieve good resolution different proportions of solvents like acetonitrile and 10mM ammonium acetate buffer of different pH conditions were tested. However, in 10mM ammonium acetate buffer with pH 3 and acetonitrile in the ratio of 80:20 achieved satisfactory results at a flow rate of 1 ml/ min measured at a detection of 257nm. The chromatogram of optimized standard is shown in Figure 5. The system suitability parameters such as retention time, resolution, tailing factor and

theoretical plates for optimized standard mixture chromatogram is tabulated in Table 8.

Method Validation

Linearity

Linearity was studied by analysing five standard solutions in the range of 1 – 5 µg/ml for Mangiferin by UV-Visible Spectrophotometry and RP-HPLC. Calibration curves with concentration versus absorbance or peak area were plotted for each method. Linearity was measured by using calibration data, regression analysis as well as coefficient of correlation. The regression data is displayed in Table 1. The correlation coefficient (r^2) of Mangiferin was found to be 0.999 and 0.998 for UV and RP-HPLC methods respectively. The linearity graphs were shown in Figure 4 & 6. This shows better detector response in different concentration for both methods.

Precision

A minimum of three determinations per concentration should be used to measure precision [14]. Precision of the analytical method was demonstrated by, intra-day precision, inter-day precision and repeatability. % RSD was calculated for both methods and results are represented in Table 2, 3 & 4. The coefficient of variation (%RSD) was less than 2% which shows the methods were precise.

Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of quantitation (LOQ)

The limit of detection and quantitation of the drugs for both methods were calculated with standard deviation and slope. The LOD and LOQ of each method was calculated and represented in Table 5.

LOD and LOQ of were calculated by using the following formula,

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \cdot \sigma / S$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \cdot \sigma / S$$

where, σ = standard deviation and S = slope

Robustness

Robustness of the UV spectrophotometry analytical method was determined by the analysis of appropriate concentrations of Mangiferin at different wavelengths (257±2nm). Values of % RSD were calculated and are shown in Table 6.

Ruggedness

Ruggedness is the ability to replicate results from an analyst and instrument under normal and expected operational conditions [15]. Appropriate concentrations of Mangiferin were analysed by different analyst. % RSD was calculated using regression coefficients obtained on different analysts and values are shown in Table 7.

System suitability

The determination of the system suitability of RP-HPLC method was accomplished by using the concentration of 3 µg/ml. The system suitability was assessed based on the retention time, peak area, theoretical plates, and asymmetry factor [16]. The optimized method is acceptable as system suitability parameters are valid as they passed the criteria of acceptability, as shown in Table 8.

DISCUSSION

UV-Visible spectrophotometry

For Mangiferin, the parameters of the UV-visible spectrophotometric method were determined. For Mangiferin, the correlation coefficient (r^2) was 0.999. This demonstrates improved detector response across a range of concentrations. This proposed method was validated as per ICH Q2R1

guidelines. LOD and LOQ indicates the sensitivity of the method. The coefficient of variation (% RSD) was less than 2% which shows the method was precise. As a result, a simple, sensitive, and precise analytical method for estimating Mangiferin by UV-visible spectrophotometry has been developed and validated in accordance with guidelines.

RP-HPLC

The working conditions for the RP-HPLC method were established for Mangiferin in bulk form. The correlation coefficient (r^2) for Mangiferin was 0.998. This demonstrates an improved detector response at various drug concentrations. This proposed method was validated as per ICH Q2R1 guidelines. LOD and LOQ indicates the sensitivity of the method. The coefficient of variation (% RSD) was less than 2% which shows the method was precise. According to the cited research article, the retention time of Mangiferin was in the range of 6.1 to 18.9 mins [16-25]. But as per the newly developed analytical method, retention time was found to be 2.9 min for Mangiferin by using flow rate of 1 ml/ min and the elution was completed within 5 min. Hence, Simple, sensitive and accurate analytical method has been developed and validated as per guidelines for the estimation of Mangiferin in bulk form by RP-HPLC.

Table 1: Regression data

Parameters	UV	RP-HPLC
Range	1-5 µg/ml.	1-5 µg/ml.
R ²	0.999	0.9989
Slope	0.0896	144925.2
Y-intercept	-0.017	382264.6

Table 2: Intra-day precision data

Parameters	UV	RP-HPLC
Concentration (µg/ ml)	3	3
Standard deviation	0.000577	5789.18
%RSD	0.227901	0.713535

Table 3: Inter-day precision data

Parameters	UV	RP-HPLC
Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	3	3
Standard deviation	0.000577	6365.432
%RSD	0.227901	0.78255

Table 4: Repeatability data

Parameters	UV	RP-HPLC
Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	3	3
Standard deviation	0.000516	5687.361
%RSD	0.203841	0.699947

Table 5: LOD and LOQ data

Drug	UV		RP-HPLC	
	LOD	LOQ	LOD	LOQ
Mangiferin	5.21864 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	15.8140 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	5.220544 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	15.81983 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

Table 6: Robustness

Parameter	Changes done	Absorbance (UV)	Peak area (RP-HPLC)
Detection wavelength	255 nm	0.253	806080
	257 nm	0.254	807790
	259 nm	0.253	816833
%RSD		0.227901	0.713154

Table 7: Ruggedness

Concentration	Parameters	Absorbance (UV)	Peak area (RP-HPLC)
3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Analyst 1	0.253	806080
	Analyst 2	0.254	816793
%RSD		0.2789376	0.933559

Table 8: System suitability parameters of RP-HPLC

Parameters	Mangiferin
Retention time	2.9 min
Peak area	806080
Theoretical plate	2275
Tailing factor	1.16

Table 9: UV spectrophotometry analytical method validation parameters

PARAMETERS	UV	RP-HPLC
Λ_{max}	257nm	257nm
Regression equation ($y=mx+c$)	$y=0.0896x-0.017$	$y=144925x+382265$
Regression coefficient (r^2)	0.9997	0.9989
Limit of detection (LOD)	5.21864	5.220544
Limit of quantitation (LOQ)	15.8140	15.81983
Repeatability indicated by % RSD for Mangiferin (3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.203841	0.699947
% RSD for Mangiferin 3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (Inter-day precision)	0.2279	0.78255
% RSD for Mangiferin 3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (Intra-day precision)	0.2279	0.713535
Robustness indicated by % RSD ($\Lambda_{\text{max}} \pm 2\text{nm}$)	0.227901	0.713154
Ruggedness indicated by % RSD (different analysts)	0.230415	0.933559

Figure 2: Spectrum of Mangiferin (3 µg/ml) at 257 nm

Figure 3: Overlain spectra of standard solution of Mangiferin

Figure 4: Linearity graph of Mangiferin at 257nm for UV-visible spectroscopy

Figure 5: Representative chromatogram of Mangiferin at 257nm for RP-HPLC

Figure 6: Linearity graph of Mangiferin at 257nm for RP-HPLC

CONCLUSION

UV-visible spectrophotometry

UV spectroscopic method was developed for the estimation of Mangiferin in bulk form and validated as per ICH guidelines. In this UV spectroscopic method for the estimation of drug, methanol and water was selected as a solvent. The UV scanning at 200-400nm for Mangiferin showed that 257nm is the suitable wavelength for detection as per maximum absorbance. Linearity showed good relationship over the concentration range of 1-5µg/ml for Mangiferin and the correlation coefficient was found to be 0.999 at 257nm. The LOD and LOQ were found to be 5.21 µg/ml, 15.81 µg/ml at 257nm. %RSD was found

to be $\leq 2\%$. Thus, the developed analytical method was simple, economical, less time consuming and all the validation parameters were within the limits.

RP-HPLC

RP-HPLC method was developed for the estimation of Mangiferin and validated as per ICH guidelines. With Shim pack Solar C₈ Column, the drug got eluted with good peak and the pressure was within the limit. This method gives reliable results with short analysis time using mobile phase of 10mM ammonium acetate buffer (pH 3) and acetonitrile in the ratio of 80: 20. Retention time was found to be 2.9 min. System suitability parameters were in the desired limit. This method

has been developed and optimized as per ICH Q₂ (R₁) guidelines. Validation parameters, linearity and correlation coefficient was found to be 1-5 µg/ml and 0.998 respectively. Precision was found to be ≤ 2%. LOD and LOQ were found to be 5.22 µg/ml, 15.81 µg/ml. In system suitability, tailing factor was 1.16 and theoretical plates were 2275. % RSD for all the validation parameters were within the limit (NMT 2.0). Thus, the developed analytical method was simple, economical, less time consuming and all the validation parameters were within the limits.

ABBREVIATIONS

RP-HPLC- Reverse Phase-High Performance Liquid Chromatography, UV- Ultra Violet, ICH- International Council for Harmonization, RSD- Relative Standard Deviation, LOD- Limit of Detection, LOQ- Limit of Quantitation, NMT- Not more than, µg/ml- Micro gram per milli litre.

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REFERENCES

1. Imran M, Arshad MS, Butt MS, Kwon JH, Arshad MU, Sultan MT. Mangiferin: a natural miracle bioactive compound against lifestyle-related disorders. *Lipids Health Dis.* 2017;16(1):84. doi:10.1186/s12944-017-0449-y
2. Jyotshna, Khare P, Singh DP. Mangiferin: A review of sources and interventions for biological activities. *Biofactors.* 2016;42(5):504-514. doi:10.1002/biof.1308
3. Mei S, Perinbam K, Rajesh R, Durairaj P, Srinivasan V. Mangiferin: a review of dietary sources, absorption, metabolism, bioavailability, and safety. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr.* 2023;63(18):3046-3064. doi:10.1080/10408398.2021.1983767
4. Castro-Muñoz R, Gornicka A, Ghaffari-Bohlender A, Garcia-Brand AJ, Simon E, Boczkaj G. Mangiferin: A comprehensive review on its extraction, purification and uses in food systems. *Adv Colloid Interface Sci.* 2024;329:103188. doi:10.1016/j.cis.2024.103188
5. Khurana RK, Kaur R, Lohan S, Singh KK, Singh B. Mangiferin: a promising anticancer bioactive. *Pharm Pat Anal.* 2016;5(3):169-181. doi:10.4155/ppa-2016-0003
6. Sanugul K, Akao T, Li Y, Kakiuchi N, Nakamura N, Hattori M. Isolation of a human intestinal bacterium that transforms mangiferin to norathyriol and inducibility of the enzyme that cleaves a C-glucosyl bond. *Biol Pharm Bull.* 2005;28(9):1672-1678. doi:10.1248/bpb.28.1672
7. Haynes LJ. Polyhydroxyxanthones. *Adv Carbohydr Chem.* 1963;18:227-258. Shaoying Hou, Fang Wang, Yingmei Li, Ying Li, Maoqing Wang, Dianjun Sun, Changhao Sun. Pharmacokinetic study of mangiferin in human plasma after oral administration, *Food Chemistry*, Volume 132, Issue 1, 2012, Pages 289-294, ISSN 0308-8146, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2011.10.079>.
8. Shaoying Hou, Fang Wang, Yingmei Li, Ying Li, Maoqing Wang, Dianjun Sun, Changhao Sun. Pharmacokinetic study of mangiferin in human plasma after oral administration, *Food Chemistry*, Volume 132, Issue 1, 2012, Pages 289-294, ISSN 0308-8146, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2011.10.079>.

9. Naveen P, Lingaraju HB, Prasad KS. Rapid development and validation of improved reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography method for the quantification of mangiferin, a polyphenol xanthone glycoside in *Mangifera indica*. *Pharmacognosy Res.* 2017;9(2):215-219. doi:10.4103/0974-8490.204652
10. Joubert E, Botha M, Maicu C, De Beer D, Manley M. Rapid screening methods for estimation of mangiferin and xanthone contents of *Cyclopia subternata* plant material. *S Afr J Bot.* 2012;82:113-122. doi:10.1016/j.sajb.2012.07.020
11. Patel M, Patel T, Parmar K, Mishra B. Development and validation of HPTLC method for simultaneous estimation of mangiferin and β -sitosterol in polyherbal formulation. *Int J Pharm Sci Res.* 2020;11(11):5792-5798.
12. Willard, Merritt, Dean, Settle, *Instrumental methods of analysis*, 7th edition, CBS Publishers, New Delhi, 1986, 1-9.
13. Rajashri R Kulkarni, Dipti Phadtare, Ravindranath Saudagar. UV Spectrophotometric Method Development and Validation of Fluticasone Propionate, *Asian Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical Science*, 6(2):135, 2016/01/01. DOI:10.5958/2231-5659.2016.00019.9
14. Whitmire ML, Bryan P, Henry TR, Holbrook J, Lehmann P, Mollitor T, Ohorodnik S, Reed D, Wietgreffe HD. Nonclinical dose formulation analysis method validation and sample analysis. *AAPS J.* 2010 Dec;12(4):628-34. DOI: 10.1208/s12248-010-9226-9.
15. Bieke Dejaeger, Yvan Vander Heyden. Ruggedness and robustness testing, *Journal of Chromatography A*, 2007, 1158(1-2):138-57. DOI:10.1016/j.chroma.2007.02.086
16. Sojitra, R.G., Chotaliya, U.J. Analytical method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of Fimasartan Potassium Trihydrate and Cilnidipine in synthetic mixture by HPLC for the treatment of hypertension stage-II. *Futur J Pharm Sci* 7, 189 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43094-021-00336-x>
17. Khemeshwari L. Sarve, Atul T. Hemke, Tanvi M. Quality by design approach to analytical RP-HPLC method development and its validation. *Journal of Global Trends in Pharmaceutical Sciences* 2019; 6972-6983.
18. Kumar P, Srivastava V, Kumar L. Development of new reversed-phase HPLC method for the determination of Mangiferin in *Mangifera indica* Linn. *Biosci Biotechnol Res Asia* 2008;5(1)
19. Naveen P, Lingaraju HB, Prasad KS. Rapid development and validation of improved reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography method for the quantification of mangiferin, a polyphenol xanthone glycoside in *Mangifera indica*. *Phcog Res* 2017; 9:215-9.
20. Xiejun Zhang, Benwei Su, Jing Li, Yonghua Li, Dong Lu, Kaixin Zhu, Hehuan Pei and Minghui Zhao. Analysis by RP-HPLC of Mangiferin Component Correlation between Medicinal *Loranthus* and their Mango Host Trees, *Journal of Chromatographic Science* 2014;52:1-4 December 17, 2012. DOI:10.1093/chromsci/bms196
21. Yuni Retnaningtyas, NiaKristiningrum. Stability Indicating RP-HPLC for Quantification Mangiferin of extract of three species Mango Leaves. *Indonesian journal of chemical research* 2020.15-20.
22. Shireesha JR, Kumar G, Mutalik S, Nandakumar K. Mangiferin analysis: comprehensive RP-HPLC method development and validation in both bulk and

- pharmaceutical dosage forms. *Res J Pharm Technol.* 2024;17(11):5230-5234. doi:10.52711/0974-360X.2024.00800.
23. García C, Felipe A, Naessens T, Foubert K, Delgado R, Mora C, Martínez V. Validation of an analytical method by HPLC applicable to the Cuban mangiferin. *Ars Pharm.* 2018;59(4):227-233. doi:10.30827/ars.v59i4.7430.
24. Retnaningtyas Y, Kristiningrum N, Renggani H, Sary I. Stability indicating RP-HPLC for quantification mangiferin in extract of three species mango leaves. *Indo J Chem Res.* 2020;8(1):15-20. doi:10.30598/ijcr.2020.8-yun.
25. Gowda N, Kumar P, Panghal S, Rajshree M. ICH guidance in practice: validated reversed-phase HPLC method for the determination of active mangiferin from extracts of *Mangifera indica* Linn. *J Chromatogr Sci.* 2010;48(2):156-160. doi:10.1093/chromsci/48.2.156.
26. Bhavna Patel, Henisha Patel, Madanmohansinh Gohil, Shraddha Parmar. Development and Validation of first order derivative spectroscopic method for simultaneous estimation of Mangiferin and Berberin HCL in bulk and synthetic mixture. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research.* 2020; 5792-5798.
27. Chatwal G R, Anand S K. Instrumental methods of chemical analysis. Himalaya publishing house. 2002; 5: 2.624-2.639.
28. Drug bank: <http://go.drugbank.com/>
29. ICH Q2 (R1), Validation of analytical procedures, in: Proceedings of the International Conference on Harmonisation, 2005.
30. PubChem: <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>
31. Sharma B. K, Instrumental methods of chemical analysis, 25th edition, Goel publishing house, 2006, 286-288.
32. Skoog, Holler, Nieman, Instrumental analysis, 5th edition, Thomson, 2006, 725-727.
33. Tripathi K D. Essentials of medical pharmacology. Jay Pee brother's medical publishers (P) Ltd. 2008; 6: p.539-41.
34. Vijaya Shastry, Ashish Haldankar and Nitin Kadam. HPLC Estimation of Mangiferin in *Salacia chinensis* Linn. *Asian J. Chem.* Vol. 21, No. 9 (2009), 6679-6682.

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